

PSYCHOSOMATIC FACTOR OF CHILDREN'S DISEASES

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There is no organ or tissue in the body without the involvement of the nervous system. That is why there is a saying among the people that "All diseases are caused by nerves". It has a great meaning. The nervous system directs and controls all the activities of the body. Any process does not take place without the participation of the nervous system. All kinds of functions, such as the flow of tears, the release of sweat, the acceleration of blood flow in the blood vessels, and the release of urine, take place under the direct participation and control of the nervous system.

The part of the nervous system that controls the activity of internal organs is called the autonomic nervous system. The autonomic nervous system is divided into sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system. Together, these two control the internal organs. Therefore, as a result of psychosomatic disorders, various diseases occur in the body. The family is a part of society, the main socialization process of a person takes place in the family, the breakdown of family relationships causes the emergence of one or another pathology. The part of the nervous system that controls the activity of internal organs is called the autonomic nervous system. The autonomic nervous system is divided into sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system. Together, these two control the internal organs. Therefore, as a result of psychosomatic disorders, various diseases occur in the body. The family is a part of society, the main socialization process of a person takes place in the family, the breakdown of family relationships causes the emergence of one or another pathology. 2. High sensitivity of each member of the family to the stress of the other; 3. Weakness of the ability to change the rules in the rigidity of mutual relations in changing situations; 4. Avoid expressing one's opinion and openly discussing disputes; 5. In many cases, the child's illness plays the role of a stabilizer (balancer) in marital disputes.

In other words, the main condition of health is the mental peace of the family. Therefore, if parents are psychologically skilled, understand, value their children, can give the necessary "amount" of positive emotions and, most importantly, love and care for each other, the child will be stress-resistant and naturally healthy. The list of deviations in parenting styles can be filled with the following: choosing characteristics of women, men or children, expanding the sphere of parental feelings, fear of separation from the child, lack of development of parental feelings, seeing one's own negative characteristics in the child, transferring conflicts between spouses to the field of education.

A child who gets sick a lot puts any mother in a very difficult situation. Endless doctor's appointments, searching for a good doctor, tests, medications, sick leave, and the agony of being locked inside four walls for weeks. What is the reason for the child to be sick so often?

Mental problems

They can cause various diseases called psychosomatic. Stresses, difficult experiences, exciting moments strongly damage children's immunity. In general, extreme joy and intense sadness can make a person depressed, but they also burn without having a negative effect on the internal organs.

Problems during pregnancy

According to some data, development problems in the mother's womb, difficult pregnancy and childbirth, and infections transferred from the expectant mother also damage the newborn's immunity.

Premature birth

If the baby is born prematurely, he is also in the group at risk of frequent diseases.

Allergy

It does not matter what exactly the child reacts to. Medical professionals have proven that one gene is responsible for all of atopic dermatitis, food allergies, pollinosis, bronchial asthma and nasopharyngeal infections. It is also passed down from generation to generation.

Not eating properly

If the child's diet lacks vitamins, protein, microelements, or fiber, or if he is fed with artificial foods, this will not leave a mark on the immune system.

Wrong lifestyle

If the child sits at home, rarely goes out, does not play sports and does not play active games in the fresh air, the risk of catching the virus is higher. The same can be said about children who travel a lot on public transport, spend a lot of

time in closed groups, go to kindergarten, participate in various activities and places where people gather.

Based on the above, the parenting style is a form of communication of parents with a child in a generalized, specific, characteristic and unusual way, a form of attitude towards a child. It can be assumed that deviations in family relationships cause the formation of certain psychosomatic disorders. Disease - on the one hand, is a method of adaptation to the environment, and on the other hand, it is a negative factor. Unexpressed anger, fear, and guilt lead to blockages in the body, which eventually turn into diseases of one or another organ or part of the body. These emotional states are then reflected in somatic health. In this case, parents' prohibitions on feelings or frequent destructive conflicts have a negative effect on the psychosomatic health of their children. Even if there is peace in the family, stress or mental injury can lead to psychosomatic diseases, therefore, if psychotherapeutic help is provided along with medical treatment, the result in the child's physical and mental condition will be more effective.

